

Relation between Thrombus Burden and Major Adverse Cardiac Event (MACE) in Patients with ST-Segment Elevation Myocardial Infarction Treated by Primary Percutaneous Coronary Intervention

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Abstract

Background: A high thrombus burden (HTB) is recognized as an independent predictor of major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE) and infarct-related artery stent thrombosis in patients with ST-elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) treated with drug-eluting stents. HTB is associated with procedural complications such as no-reflow, slow flow, and distal embolization, which may result in larger infarct size, left ventricular systolic dysfunction (LVSD), and poorer clinical outcomes. Despite this, the clinical impact of HTB has often been underestimated due to limitations in conventional imaging modalities. **Methods:** This multicenter observational study included 417 consecutive STEMI patients who underwent primary percutaneous coronary intervention (PPCI) at four cardiac centers between December 2019 and December 2020. Eligible patients presented within 12 hours of symptom onset (up to 24 hours in selected high-risk cases) and fulfilled standard ECG criteria for STEMI. Ischemic time was defined as the interval from onset of persistent chest pain to first balloon inflation. HTB was defined as TIMI thrombus grade 4 or 5. LVSD was defined as an ejection fraction (EF) <50% assessed by transthoracic echocardiography on the day of intervention. MACE comprised cardiac death, LVSD, and stroke. **Results:** The cohort was predominantly male (75.5%), with a mean age of 55.5 years. HTB was observed in over 80% of patients, most commonly TIMI grade 5. TIMI 3 flow was achieved in more than 75% of cases. MACE occurred in 41.7% of patients, mainly driven by LVSD. Mortality was low (0.7%), while stroke occurred in six patients. More than 90% of patients with MACE had HTB. Angiographically visible distal embolization and no-reflow were exclusively associated with MACE. **Conclusion:** High thrombus burden is strongly associated with adverse cardiovascular outcomes in STEMI patients treated with primary PCI and remains a critical determinant of prognosis.

Introduction

ST-elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) is a clinical syndrome characterized by prolonged myocardial ischemia resulting from acute coronary artery occlusion, manifested by typical chest pain, persistent ST-segment elevation on electrocardiography, and subsequent release of cardiac biomarkers indicating myocardial necrosis [1]. The fundamental pathophysiological mechanism underlying STEMI is rupture or erosion of an atherosclerotic plaque with

superimposed intracoronary thrombus formation, leading to partial or complete interruption of coronary blood flow [2]. The extent of intracoronary thrombus plays a critical role in determining both procedural success and clinical outcomes. A high thrombus burden (HTB) has been associated with increased infarct size through microvascular obstruction, distal embolization, and impaired myocardial reperfusion, ultimately resulting in deterioration of left ventricular systolic function during and after primary percutaneous

More Information

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thrombus, burden, (MACE), ST-Segment, myocardial, infarction, PPCI.

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coronary intervention (PPCI) [3]. Accumulating evidence indicates that HTB is an independent predictor of major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE), including stent thrombosis of the infarct-related artery (IRA-ST), particularly in patients treated with drug-eluting stents (DES) for STEMI [4,5]. Despite advances in pharmacological therapy and interventional techniques, the mechanisms and clinical implications of plaque-associated thrombus remain incompletely understood. The prognostic impact of HTB has historically been underestimated, partly due to the limited spatial resolution of conventional imaging modalities such as intravascular ultrasound (IVUS) and computed tomography, which may fail to accurately characterize thrombus composition and extent [4,6]. Identifying determinants of intracoronary thrombus burden may therefore contribute to improved risk stratification and optimization of interventional strategies in STEMI patients undergoing PPCI. Clinical outcomes after STEMI vary substantially depending on baseline patient characteristics; however, angiographic and echocardiographic findings remain powerful predictors of prognosis [5,7]. Although PPCI is a class I recommendation in all major international guidelines and represents the preferred reperfusion strategy for STEMI, restoration of epicardial patency does not invariably translate into effective myocardial reperfusion or preservation of left ventricular function (8). Patients with a large thrombus burden are particularly prone to complications such as no-reflow, slow flow, and angiographically visible distal embolization, all of which adversely affect myocardial perfusion and clinical outcomes [3,9]. HTB has also been linked to a higher incidence of early and late complications, including left ventricular systolic dysfunction (LVSD), malignant arrhythmias, heart failure, cardiac rupture, and stroke, resulting in worse short- and long-term prognosis [10]. Myocardial necrosis following acute MI initiates ventricular remodeling, characterized by left ventricular dilatation and progressive systolic dysfunction, which is a major determinant of heart failure development and mortality [5-7]. Given the strong pathophysiological and prognostic links between thrombus burden, impaired reperfusion, and adverse outcomes, evaluating the relationship between intracoronary thrombus burden and in-hospital MACE is of considerable clinical importance. Therefore, the present study aims to assess the association between angiographically determined thrombus burden and in-hospital major adverse cardiovascular events, including cardiac death, stroke, and LV systolic dysfunction, in patients with STEMI undergoing primary PCI.

Methodology

This prospective multicenter observational study included patients presenting with ST-elevation

myocardial infarction (STEMI) who underwent primary percutaneous coronary intervention (PPCI) at Ibn Al-Nafees, Al-Najaf, Al-Nasiriyah, and Ibn Al-Betar cardiac centers between December 2019 and December 2020. Patient enrollment was performed sequentially across centers in accordance with Iraqi Board training rotation requirements. Eligible patients presented within 12 hours of symptom onset (up to 24 hours in cases of cardiogenic shock, persistent chest pain, or significant arrhythmias) and had diagnostic ECG criteria for STEMI (ST elevation ≥ 1 mm in ≥ 2 contiguous leads, ≥ 2 mm in V1–V3, or new left bundle branch block). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Clinical Assessment and Procedures

Baseline demographic data, cardiovascular risk factors, prior cardiovascular history, medication use, and smoking status were recorded at admission. Laboratory investigations included baseline troponin, random blood glucose, blood urea, serum creatinine, and complete blood count. Ischemic time was defined as the interval from onset of continuous ischemic chest pain to first balloon inflation and categorized as <6 hours, 6–12 hours, or >12 hours. All patients received aspirin (300 mg), clopidogrel (600 mg) or ticagrelor (180 mg), and intravenous unfractionated heparin prior to PPCI. Procedures were performed by experienced interventional cardiologists via femoral access using 6F or 7F sheaths. Angiographic assessment included infarct-related artery identification, thrombus burden grading, and final Thrombolysis in Myocardial Infarction (TIMI) flow.

Definitions and Outcomes

Angiographic thrombus burden was graded using the TIMI thrombus scale (grades 0–5), with high thrombus burden (HTB) defined as grades 4–5. Major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE) were defined as the composite of cardiac death, stroke, and left ventricular systolic dysfunction (LVSD). LVSD was defined as an ejection fraction (EF) <50%, assessed by transthoracic echocardiography on the same day of intervention. No-reflow and angiographically visible distal embolization were defined according to standard criteria.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 22. Categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages and compared using chi-square tests. Continuous variables were compared using independent t-tests or Mann–Whitney U tests as appropriate. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

This is a cross-sectional observational study that conducted from December 2019 to December 2020 in four cardiac centers in Iraq. Included in the study 417 patients who presented with acute ST elevation MI 315 (75.5%) were male. And the mean age was 55.47.

Hypertension and DM were found in 44.6% and 32.4 % respectively. More than 90 % of the patients included

in the study presented with ischemic time less than 12 hours (see Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic Features of the Patients

Variable	Number	%
Sex		
Male	315	75.5 %
Female	102	24.5 %
Age	55.47 (33-80) range	57.5
Diabetes mellitus	135	32.4 %
Hypertension	186	44.6 %
Smoker	210	50.3 %
Ischemic Time		
Less than 6 hours	162	38.8 %
6-12 hours	231	55.4 %
More than 12 hours	24	5.8 %

Regarding the finding during catheterization half of the patients had left anterior descending artery (LAD) as infarcted related artery (IRA) and more than 80% had

high thrombus burden (HTB) and the majority of them were G5 as shown in Table 2. TIMI 3 was achieved in more than three quarters of the patients.

Table 2: Catheterization Finding

Variable	Number	%
IRA		
LAD	213	51.1
LCX	51	12.2
RCA	153	36.7
Thrombus Burden		
HTB	348	83.5
LOW TB	69	16.5
Thrombus Burden Scale		
G0	0	0
G1	0	0
G2	9	2.2
G3	60	14.4
G4	102	24.5
G5	246	59.0
Post Procedure Timi Flow		
T1	3	0.7
T2	96	23
T3	318	76.3
AVDE		
With distal embolization	18	4.3
Without distal embolization	399	95.7
No reflow		
With no-reflow	51	12.2
Without no-reflow	366	87.8

The occurrence of major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE) was observed in 41.7%, predominantly associated with a low ejection fraction (EF) below 50%.

The mortality rate was 0.7%, and six patients experienced a stroke (see Table 3).

Table 3. Clinical Outcome of the Patients after PPCI

Variable	Number	%
MACE		
without MACE	243	58.3
With MACE	174	41.7
Post cath. EF		
more than 50 %	246	58.9
40 – 50 %	132	31.7
30 – 40 %	24	5.8
Less than 30 %	15	3.6
Post cath. Stroke		
Without stroke	411	98.6
With stroke	6	1.4
Post cath. Death		
Death	3	0.7
Alive	414	99.3

Note: MACE - major adverse cardiovascular events; EF - ejection fraction.

As demonstrated in Table 4, over 90% of patients who experienced MACE had hypertension. The majority of these cases exhibited an ischemic duration ranging from 6 to 12 hours, while 21 patients experienced ischemic times exceeding 12 hours. Most of these cases involved the LAD as the infarct-related artery. HTB, ischemic time, and the infarct-related artery were

considered statistically significant factors in the development of MACE. Regarding AVDE (angiographic visible distal embolization) and NRF (no-reflow), all of these patients experienced MACE. Age and diabetes mellitus were not statistically significant factors in the development of MACE.

Table 4: Factors Related to Development MACE

Variable	YES (N =174)	NO (N=243)		
Variable	MACE		95% CI	p value
HTB	159	189	1.2-1.33	0.001
LTB	15	54		
Ischemic Time			1.1-1.2	
Less than 6 hour	6	156		
6-12 hours	147	84		0.001
More than 12 h.	21	3		
IRA			0.42- 2.3	<0.0001
LAD	138	75		
LCX	9	42		
RCA	27	126		
Hypertenstion			0.745- 1.443	0.003
Yes	96	90		
No	78	153		
DM			0.32- 12.4	0.88
yes	57	78		
no	117	165		
Sex			0.26 -1.034	0.027
Male	141	174		
Female	33	69		
Age	56.62 mean 174	54.65 mean 243	0.4 – 2.931	0.84
AVDE			1.35 -1.458	0.0001
Without-De	156	243		
With De	18	0		
Noreflow				

Yes	51	0	1.034 -1.998	<0.0001
No	123	243		

Note: LAD left ant .descending artery , LCX left circumflex artery , RCA right coronary artery. HTB high thrombus burden. LTB low thrombus burden. IRA infracted related artery. AVDE angiographic visible distal embolization. DM diabetes mellitus.

Table (5) illustrates the factors associated with the development of angiographically visible distal embolization (AVDE). HTB and LAD, as IRA, were observed in all eighteen patients who developed AVDE.

More than half of the cases exhibited an ischemic time exceeding 12 hours; therefore, these factors were regarded as statistically significant in the development of AVDE.

Table 5: Factors Related to Angiographic Visible Distal Embolization

Variable	AVDE		P value
	Yes N=18	No N=399	
HTB	18	330	<0.0001
LTB	0	69	
IRA			0.0001
LAD	18	195	
LCX	0	51	
RCA	0	153	
Ischemic Time			<0.0001
Less than 6 hours	0	162	
6-12 hours	6	225	
More than 12 h.	12	12	
DM			0.103
With DM	9	126	
Without DM	9	273	
Hypertention			0.327
With HT	6	180	
Without HT	12	219	
Sex			0.433
Male	15	300	
Female	3	99	
Age (mean ±SD)	55.83 (18)	55.4 (399)	0.815

Note: LAD - left ant .descending artery; LCX - left circumflex artery; RCA - right coronary artery; HTB - high thrombus burden; LTB - low thrombus burden; IRA - infracted related artery; AVDE - angiographic visible distal embolization; DM - diabetes mellitus.

Table (6) presents the factors associated with NRF (no reflow). All of these patients who develop NRF exhibit high thrombus burden (HTB), with the LAD appearing to be the predominant IRA, and over three-quarters of

them having an ischemic duration between 6 to 12 hours. Therefore, all of these findings are regarded as statistically significant for the development of NRF.

Table 6: Factors Related to NRF (no reflow)

Variable	No - Reflow		P value
	Yes N=51	No N= 366	
Sex			0.024
Male	46	270	
Female	6	96	
Hypertention			0.202
With HT	27	159	
Without HT	24	207	
DM			

With DM	24	111	0.01
Without DM	27	255	
Ischemic time			<0.0001
Less than 6 h.	3	159	
6-12 hours	39	192	
More than 12 h.	9	15	
IRA			<0.0001
LAD	42	171	
LCX	0	51	
RCA	9	144	
Thrombus Burden			0.001
HTB	51	297	
LTB	0	69	

Note: HTB - high thrombus burden; LTB - low thrombus burden; LAD - left ant descending artery; LCX - left circumflex artery; RCA - right coronary artery; IRA infarcted related artery. DM diabetes mellitus

Table 7 presents the incidence of IRA in relation to HTB. LAD was observed in approximately 50% of all patients with hypertension, with the RCA being the second most common after the LAD. Approximately 56% of patients with HTB exhibited an ischemic time ranging from 6 to

12 hours, while all patients presenting after more than 12 hours had HTB. All patients who develop AVDE and NRF exhibit HTB. Age was not statistically significant in relation to thrombus burden.

Table 7: Factors Associated with Thrombus Burden

Thrombus Burden	HTB	LTB	p value
	n=348	n=69	
IRA			0.03
LAD	177	36	
LCX	33	18	
RCA	138	15	
ISCHEMIC Time			0.001
Less than 6 hours	126	36	
Between 6-12 hours	198	33	
More than 12 hours	24	0	
AVDE			<0.0001
without DE	330	69	
With DE	18	0	
NRF			0.001
Without NRF	297	69	
With NRF	51	0	
Age	53.8±11.4	57.3±7.3	0.72

Note: AVDE - angiographic visible distal embolization; LAD - left ant descending artery; LCX - left circumflex artery; RCA - right coronary artery; IRA - infarcted related artery; NRF - no reflow.

In Table 8, HTB was observed in 348 patients, accounting for 84% of all participants in the study. Among these, 44% exhibited LVSD (EF less than 50%), and all individuals with an EF below 40% had HTB. All

patients who experience a stroke have hypertension. And two out of three patients who died had hypertension.

Table 8: MACE Associated with Thrombus Burden

Thrombus Burden	HTB	LTB	p value
	n=348	n=69	
Post cath. EF%			0.001
More 50	195	51	
Between 40-50	114	18	
Between 40-30	24	0	

Less than 30	15	0	
Stroke			
With stroke	6		0.01
Without stroke	342		
Death			
Died	2	1	0.5
Alive	346	68	

Note: EF - ejection fraction; HTB - high thrombus burden; LTB - low thrombus burden.

Discussion

Primary percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) is the treatment of choice for patients presenting with acute ST-elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) and has consistently demonstrated superiority over fibrinolytic therapy in terms of survival, reinfarction, and stroke reduction [19]. The introduction of coronary stenting has further improved both short- and long-term outcomes. Nevertheless, despite substantial advances in interventional techniques and adjunctive pharmacotherapy, patients with angiographically evident intracoronary thrombus continue to experience a higher incidence of in-hospital major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE). In the present study, the study population was predominantly male with a mean age of approximately 55 years, and a high prevalence of traditional cardiovascular risk factors, including diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and smoking. Angiographic assessment demonstrated a remarkably high prevalence of high thrombus burden (HTB), with TIMI grade 5 thrombus observed in 59% and grade 4 in 24.5% of patients. Consequently, more than 80% of the cohort had HTB, emphasizing the substantial thrombotic milieu among STEMI patients undergoing PPCI in our setting. Importantly, HTB was present in over 90% of patients who developed in-hospital MACE, underscoring its strong association with adverse outcomes. Ischemic time emerged as a key determinant of prognosis. Although the majority of patients presented within 12 hours of symptom onset, more than half arrived between 6 and 12 hours, which remains longer than recommended by current guidelines. Patients with ischemic time exceeding 6 hours, particularly those presenting after 12 hours, had a significantly higher incidence of MACE ($p=0.001$), a finding consistent with prior reports demonstrating a direct relationship between prolonged ischemic duration and worse clinical outcomes [11,12]. Delayed presentation in our cohort likely reflects logistical and infrastructural limitations, which continue to challenge timely STEMI care. Left anterior descending artery (LAD) involvement was the most frequent infarct-related artery and was commonly associated with TIMI grade 5 thrombus. This finding is concordant with previous studies reporting LAD dominance in STEMI and its association with larger infarct size and worse prognosis [13,14]. In our analysis, HTB and infarct-

related artery were significant predictors of MACE, whereas age and diabetes mellitus were not, partially differing from earlier studies that identified these factors as independent predictors [15,16]. Left ventricular systolic dysfunction (LVSD) represented the principal contributor to MACE in the current study, affecting approximately 41% of patients. HTB, prolonged ischemic time, angiographically visible distal embolization, and no-reflow were all significantly associated with LVSD, findings that align with contemporary observational data linking impaired myocardial reperfusion to adverse ventricular remodeling and heart failure [17,18]. Furthermore, angiographically visible distal embolization and no-reflow were observed in 4.3% and 12.2% of patients, respectively, and were strongly associated with HTB. These results are consistent with previous studies demonstrating that large thrombus burden increases the risk of distal embolization and no-reflow, leading to suboptimal myocardial perfusion and increased mortality [19,20]. Overall, our findings reinforce the pivotal role of high thrombus burden, infarct-related artery, and delayed reperfusion in determining in-hospital outcomes after primary PCI, highlighting the need for strategies aimed at early presentation and optimized thrombus management to improve prognosis in STEMI patients.

Conclusion

High thrombus burden was significantly associated with MACE in patients treated with PPCI.

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